

Spectrophotometric Determination of Lanthanides with Methyl Thymol Blue in presence of Micelle Forming Cationic Detergents

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Ternary Complex systems between lanthanides, methyl thymol blue and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide are proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of minute amounts of lanthanides. The blue complex $[\text{Ln}(\text{MT})_4(\text{CTAB})_4]$ has an absorbance maximum at 640 nm. Sensitivity of the reaction ranges between 0.0031 to 0.0039 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for lighter and heavier series under the present conditions of study. The study includes the effect of pH, effect of reagent concentration, complex formation and the analytical application of the systems viz. Beer's law, photometric ranges and effect of foreign ions.

THE use of ternary complexes in spectrophotometric determination of minute amounts of metals have been proposed by certain workers¹⁻⁶ Svoboda and Chromy⁷⁻⁹ have used Xylenol orange in presence Cetyl pyridinium bromide for the spectrophotometric determination of lanthanum (III). The study of complexes of lanthanides with methyl thymol blue, in absence of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, has also been reported by many workers¹⁰⁻¹². Recently, the spectrophotometric determination of erbium in a mixture with lanthanum using methyl thymol blue, in presence of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, has been reported¹³ in the pH range of 3.8-3.9. Our results are however different from this.

The effect of micelles on methyl thymol blue has already been reported by us previously¹⁴. This paper reports the study on the ternary complex system between some of the lanthanides, methyl thymol blue and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide at pH 5.8, for developing a sensitive spectrophotometric method for the micro-determination of trace amounts of lanthanides. For the detailed experimental work, we have selected trivalent lanthanum, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium and dysprosium as representative lanthanides for lighter and heavier series.

Experimental

Reagents: Metal ion solutions ($10^{-2}M$) were prepared by dissolving 99.9% lanthanide oxides in minimum quantity of A. R. hydrochloric acid and making up the volume with distilled water. These solutions were later estimated quantitatively. Methyl Thymol Blue (abb MTB) solution ($10^{-3}M$) was made by dissolving calculated amount of the pure reagent (Reanal) in distilled water. A 20% (v/v) aqueous methanal solution ($10^{-3}M$) of cetyl. Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (abb. CTAB) was used. It was standardised by titrating against AgNO_3 solution for bromide ion content.

Apparatus: All absorbance measurements were made on Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer using matched glass cells of 10 m.m. path length. Elico pH

meter model LI-10 was used with a glass and calomel electrode assembly. pH of the solutions was adjusted with help of HCl and NaOH solutions of suitable concentration.

Results and Discussion

Spectral Studies: The absorption spectra of MTB in absence and in presence of CTAB at pH 9.5 have been reported earlier by us¹⁴. Although CTAB causes a shift in λ_{max} in alkaline range (pH 9.5) of MTB, the complex formation with lanthanides in this range could not be done due to hydrolysis. It was however observed that in the pH range of 4.5 to 6.5, where MTB is capable of binding only four equivalents of CTAB⁴, the decrease of absorbance maximum of MTB is somewhat smaller. Under these conditions, La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} form a blue coloured complex, the absorption of which shows a marked maximum at 640 nm. A typical graph for comparison of absorption spectra is given (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1

Curve A : MTB $4 \times 10^{-5}M$, $\text{Gd}^{3+} 1.6 \times 10^{-4}M$, CTAB $4 \times 10^{-4}M$
B : MTB $4 \times 10^{-5}M$, $\text{Gd}^{3+} 1.6 \times 10^{-4}M$.
C : MTB $4 \times 10^{-5}M$, CTAB, $4 \times 10^{-4}M$.
D : MTB $4 \times 10^{-5}M$.

Curved D shows the spectra of MTB alone at pH 5.8 with a λ_{max} of 440 nm, where as curve C is that of MTB in presence of CTAB (1:10 ratio) with a λ_{max} of 460 nm. When the spectra was recorded in presence of metal ion (Gd^{3+}) in the ratio of $Gd^{3+} : MTB, 1:1$ (Curve B) it shows a λ_{max} of 600 nm as reported by earlier workers¹⁰⁻¹². However, when the spectra is taken in presence of CTAB for Gd^{3+} in the ratio of 1:1:10 ($Gd^{3+} : MTB : CTAB$) (Curve A) the λ_{max} shifts to 640 nm with a large increase in absorbance at this wavelength when compared to Curve B. Thus it may be concluded that, the formatin of the complex in presence of CTAB, is accompanied by a marked increase in absorbance and a bathochromic shift of approximately 40 nm. It may further be mentioned that similar results were obtained for other lanthanide systems studied here, giving a λ_{max} of 640 nm.

Optimum Conditions for Colour Development :

The effect of pH on the absorption of the complex in presence of CTAB was studied at 640 nm. It has been found that from pH 5.2 to 5.8 the absorbance is almost constant. pH 5.8 at which the difference between the absorbance of the complex, with and without CTAB is maximum, has been chosen for further work.

The stability of the colour was studied at room temperature by measuring the absorbance at regular time intervals. The maximum absorbance was achieved only after one hour of the addition of the reactants and no chage was then observed for atleast 24 hr. All measurements were made 1 hr after the preparation of the solution. In all experiments, detergent solution was added to MTB solution. This solution was kept for atleast half an hour for micellar agregates to from, to which metal ion solution is then added. This is very important and the sequence must be followed strictly.

The effect of excess of reagent concentration on the absorbance of the complex in presence of CTAB at 640 nm shows that a two fold excess of MTB is sufficient to cause maximum colour development.

Composition and conditional formation constants :

The composition of the Lanthanide - MTB complex in presence of CTAB has been determined by the method of continuous variation and the mole ratio method. Both methods indicate that the ratio of the lanthanide :

MTB is 1:1, the composition of the complexes may therefore, be formulated as $[Ln (MTB) (CTAB)_4]$ where CTAB represents associated cetyl Trimethyl ammonium bromide ions and Ln for all trivalent lanthanide ions studied here. The formation of the complexes may be expressed by the following equation (omitting charges) $Ln + MTB (CTAB)_4 \rightleftharpoons Ln[(MTB) (CTAB)_4]$. The logarithm of the conditional formation constant, corresponding to this equilibrium, evaluated by Job's method are tabulated in Table 1.

Analytical Studies : The considerable bathochromic shift in λ_{max} of lanthanide complexes of MTB, large absorbance values at the change λ_{max} and correspondingly negligible absorbance of MTB alone in presence of CTAB, suggest a very useful application of these colour reactions in the spectrophotometric determination of minute amounts of lanthanides with MTB in presence of CTAB.

Systematic in investigation of various characteristic properties useful for analytical purposes is described here. The wavelength of study was chosen to be 640 nm at pH 5.8.

Beer's Law and photometric ranges : The linearity between the absorbance of the chelate and the metal ion in presence of CTAB was tested by varying metal ion concentration. The range for adherence to Beer's law for almost all the lanthanides studied here comes within the range of 0.27 to 3.24 p. p. m. of metal ion. The effective range for photometric determination was calculated from these data by plotting the Ringbom plot¹⁵. The values are in the range of 0.56 ppm to 1.95 ppm for these lanthanides.

Sensitivity and Molar Extinction coefficients : Molar extinction coefficients of the complexes was determined by taking a constant amount of MTB and different amounts of excess of metal ion with ten times excess of CTAB at pH 5.8. The absorbance was noted at 640 nm. The molar extinction coefficients and the sensitivities of the lanthanide complexes in presence of CTAB are tabulated below. For comparison the values of molar absorptivity of lanthanide chelates of xylenol orange are also reported. Xylenol orange is supposed to be the most sensitive reagent known for the lanthanides¹⁶. Thus, MTB in presence of CTAB can be regarded as one of quite sensitive reagents reported so far, for the spectrophotometric determination of minute amounts of lanthanides.

Effect of Foreign Ions : The effect of foreign ions was tested by 0.78 ppm of lanthanide ions and determining its concentration in presence of a large number of interfering ions. The results for Gd^{3+} system has been tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 1—EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS AND SANDELL'S SENSITIVITIES FOR THE SYSTEMS

Metal ion Ln^{3+}	Conditional formation constants log K.	Sandell's Sensitivity $\mu g/cm^2$ in presence of CTAB	Molar absorptivity of xylenol orange 16 complexes at pH 5.8 at 570 nm	Molar absorptivity in presence of CTAB
La	5.74	0.0034	19,000	45,000
Pr	5.67	0.0035	17,000	41,250
Nd	5.74	0.0031	23,000	48,750
Sm	5.74	0.0032	23,000	46,000
Gd	5.67	0.0039	20,700	37,500
Dy	5.67	0.0039	23,500	37,500

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS
0.78 ppm of Gd³⁺ taken

Ion	Amt. of interfering ion in (ppm)	Gd ³⁺ found ppm	Error %	Ion	Amt. of interfering ion in ppm	Gd ³⁺ found ppm	Error %
Ag ⁺	1.07	0.802	+2.84	Ga ³⁺	1.39	0.776	- 0.51
Ca ²⁺	1.6	0.788	+1.02	In ³⁺	2.28	0.700	-10.2
	12.8	0.800	+2.5	Tl ³⁺	1.14	0.788	+ 1.02
Sr ²⁺	7.0	0.775	-0.66	Y ³⁺	7.05	0.696	-10.7
Ba ²⁺	5.48	0.788	+1.02	Pb ²⁺	8.2	0.760	- 2.5
Mg ²⁺	9.6	0.780	±0.00	UO ₂ ²⁺	10.8	0.760	- 2.5
Be ²⁺	0.36	0.179	- 77	La ³⁺	0.27	1.8	+ 66
Mn ²⁺	2.16	0.796	+2.05	Nd ³⁺	0.30	1.56	+30
Al ³⁺	16.2	0.772	-1.02	Dy ³⁺	0.35	1.62	+51
F ⁻	15.2	0.791	+1.4	Cl ⁻	14.0	0.784	+ 0.51
Br ⁻	12.8	0.788	+1.02	I ⁻	10.1	0.772	- 1.02

It may be seen that the method suffers from the lack of specificity but the interferences are not too many. The determination is possible in the absence of other lanthanons, beryllium, indium and yttrium. The determination is possible in presence of metal ions like Ag⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺, as they can be masked by adding suitable concentration of cyanide ions. Anions like F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, do not interfere.

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